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GROUP DYNAMICS OF THE WOMEN SHGS IN ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract:-People's participation in credit delivery and recovery and linking of formal credit institutions to borrowers through intermediaries of SHGs have been recognized as a complementary mechanism for providing credit support to the rural poor. Thus the SHGs are organizations of the poor, which form an informal alliance for a common goal to be achieved collectively. As a result of the group activities, the women are able to protect themselves from all types of exploitation. An examination of group dynamics of the SHGs is important in order to assess the effectiveness of groups and sustainability of these groups to achieve the desired objective of the programme. The main objective of the study is to examine the group dynamics of women SHGs in Andhra Pradesh. Group dynamics of the SHGs included group formation, regularity of meetings, collection of savings, internal lending, interest rate for internal lending, SHG bank linkage and attended training programmes. The present study reveals that cent per cent of the SHG women have been involved in the micro credit savings. Majority of them are properly facilitated through conducting periodical meetings and training programmes for their improvement. Majority of the respondents are actively participated in group activities and follow the adequate approach by the SHGs in getting of bank linkages. Eventhough majority of the SHG women are following the SHG norms perfectly but some of the respondent's active participation in group activities was very much limited due to the lack of adequate approach of the SHGs

Keywords:Self-Help Groups, Group Dynamics, Bank Linkage, Savings and Internal Lending.

INTRODUCTION

For the development of women the Government of India evolved many women centered development programmes. The benefits derived from these programmes remained a challenge. To meet the inadequacy in response, the strategy in the 1990s shifted from development of women to women empowerment by giving them a voice in the decisions that affect their lives. It leads to implement the group strategies for women empowerment. Empowerment of women through SHGs (Self-Help Groups) strategy is a novel approach in development planning. Self-Help Group is considered as a strategy evolved by the developing nations to empower women especially rural women to leap from the state of powerlessness to powerfulness. The vision of the Self-Help Groups'

movement is to empower rural poor women for overall development of the country. (Rajani Manikonda, 2014) Self-Help Groups ensure people's participation in the development process as these are the grass root level democratic institutions of rural people.

Self-Help Group Programmes are presently being promoted as a key strategy for simultaneously dealing with both women's empowerment and poverty alleviation. Self-Help Group is a small and economically homogeneous and affinity group of 10-20 members, mostly women belonging to rural poor, voluntarily coming together for mutual benefit and support with thrift and credit as entry point. Approach of the group towards poverty alleviation should be self-help others, that is they should help the poor to help themselves. Women SHGs play an essential role in enhancing the knowledge, skill and good attitude of their members in working together for social and economic uplift of their families and communities. (Kulshrestha, 2000) without the rural women contribution in socio-economic development, the enlistment of the economy will be a day dream. Micro finance encourages the socio-economic development of rural areas.

The movement of SHG was started with the introduction of DWCRA programme in Andhra Pradesh. The mission of this movement is to make women manage themselves for social mobilization, to create self confidence, rise their self esteem through participation in socio-economic and political spheres of life. Lastly to institutionalization of the SHG programme, it was proposed to sustain the groups. (Suda Rani, 2002) The micro credit movement in India is gathering women from the grass root levels to organize themselves into SHGs. Thus the SHGs are organizations of the poor, which form an informal alliance for a common goal to be achieved collectively. As a result of the group activities, the women were able to protect themselves from all types of exploitation. Regular savings and convening of regular monthly meetings were the important activities of SHGs. Most of the groups generated sufficient money through savings. The saved amount is pooled together and used for disbursement of credit among the members to meet their immediate socio-economic needs. These groups are also linked with banks for credit to undertake income-generating activities.

People's participation in credit delivery and recovery and linking of formal credit institutions to borrowers through intermediaries of SHGs have been recognized as a complementary mechanism for providing credit support to the rural poor. In India SHGs are mushrooming in almost all parts of the country. The microfinance programme in India has emerged as not only the fastest growing and also the largest in the world having covered over 103 million poor households' access to a variety of sustainable financial services from the banking system by becoming members of nearly 8 million SHGs by end of March 2012. The balance in the saving accounts of the banks at the end of March 2012 stood at Rs. 6,551.41 crore. Among the regions, southern region is highest at Rs. 10,080 per SHG. Andhra Pradesh has been a leading state in promoting microfinance services through SHGs for women in the poorer sections of the society. In Andhra Pradesh, the SHG approach constituted the primary route towards poverty alleviation and development. (Abdul Raheem and Yasmeen Sultana, 2007) Women led SHGs in many parts of country have achieved success in bringing the women to the mainstream of decision making. The SHG in our country has become a source of inspiration for women's welfare. Now-a-days formation of SHG is a viable alternative to achieve the objectives of rural development and to get community participation in all rural development programmes.

An examination of group dynamics of the SHGs is important in order to assess the effectiveness of groups and sustainability of these groups to achieve the desired objective of the programme. The main objective of SHG programme is to empower women by providing financial assistance through bank linkage. An amount of financial assistance through bank linkage is based upon the group dynamics of the SHGs. Hence, the relationship between bank linkage and other socio-economic variables is analyzed. This enables to get an overall view of the functioning of the SHG programme. Study of group dynamics of SHG's is to identify the important dimensions contributing to their effectiveness that is the way the groups and individuals act and react to change circumstances. The group dynamics of SHGs includes different processes of SHG banks linkage like group formation, regularity of meetings, collection of savings, internal lending, interest rate of internal lending, SHG bank linkage and distribution pattern of current linkage amount among the member's.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the group dynamics of women SHGs in Andhra Pradesh.
2. To give suggestions for better functioning of SHGs in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The analysis is based on the primary data. A multi stage random sampling method is used for the study. The primary data was collected from three hundred sample SHG members who received minimum of four bank linkages in selected three sample districts of Andhra Pradesh through a well structured questionnaire by personal interview.

EXPERIENCE AS GROUP MEMBER

The experience as group member is an important factor to measure the effectiveness of the SHG. With the increase in the experience of group it becomes convenient to consolidate the activities of SHG and facilitate the members to understand the group dynamics of the SHGs. Distribution of the respondents by the years of experience in the SHGs is presented in table-1. It is evident from the table-1 that 61 per cent of the respondents have 5 to 10 years of experience as a member after joining in SHGs. Further, it shows that 25 per cent of the respondents have 10 to 15 years of experience and only 14 per cent of the respondents have above 15 years of experience. It is observed that groups with 5 to 10 years of age are higher in number. That is, year by year the number of the SHGs is increasing. This may be due to the increased levels of awareness among the respondents to join the SHGs to avail its benefits.

Table-1
Age wise Distribution of Sample Respondents

Age of the SHG (Ranges in years)	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
5 to 10 years	183	61.0
10 to 15 years	75	25.0
Above 15	42	14.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

MOTIVATION TO JOIN IN SHG

The motivation for women to join in SHGs is that they believe that working in groups enhances their socio-economic status. Women have confidence that as a group she enhances her ability to perform and meet the interpersonal needs through inclusion. The collective aspirations of group members become stronger day by day that works as a strong motivation to other non-SHG members. Distribution of the sample respondents by whom they are motivated to join in SHGs is presented in table-2. It is observed that 37 per cent of the respondents were motivated to join SHGs by other SHG members and the Government officials. Further, it is observed that 34 per cent of the respondents were motivated to join SHGs by friends and relatives, while 16.7 per cent of the respondents were motivated by neighbors and 12.3 per cent are motivated by family members. Thus, the study shows that other SHG members and Government officials like animators are playing active role in motivating women to join in SHGs. However the main motivation for women is found to be seen as benefits provided by the programme.

Table-2
Distribution of Respondents by Motivation

Source of Motivation	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Family Members	37	12.3
Friends/Relatives	102	34.0
Neighbours	50	16.7
Other SHG Members and Government Officials	111	37.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

REASONS FOR JOINING SHG

The major aim of the SHGs is to promote savings and to credit for the productive and consumption purpose. This is true because many people in the study area joins the SHGs for getting loan with less rate of interest, promote their personal savings and to earn income to improve the level of living conditions. In this study, the sample women expressed various reasons for joining the SHG. Distribution of the sample respondents by reasons for joining SHGs is given in table-3. It is evident that 57 per cent of the sample respondents have joined SHGs to get loan with low interest. Further, it is observed that 22 per cent of the respondents have joined in SHGs to save money and 13 per cent of the respondents have joined SHGs to earn income. Finally 8 per cent of respondents have joined in SHGs to improve their standard of living. Therefore it is concluded that majority of the respondents of the present study have joined in SHG for getting loan with low interest.

Table-3
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Reasons for joining in SHG

Reason for joining in SHG	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
To Save Money	66	22.0
For Getting Loan with Low Interest	171	57.0
To Earn Income	39	13.0
To Improve Standard of Living	24	8.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

Position of the Respondents in the SHG

Distribution of the respondents according to their position in group is given in the table-4. It shows that out of total 300 sample respondents, 60.7 per cent of the respondents are ordinary members in SHGs. Further, 32.3 per cent of the respondents are group leaders and only 7 per cent of respondents are holding in the position treasurer and secretary. It is observed and concluded that only 39.3 per cent of the respondents are holding positions like leaders and treasurer or secretary, rest of the respondents are the ordinary members.

Table-4
Distribution of the Respondents by their Position in SHG

Position in SHG	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Ordinary Member	182	60.7
Leader	97	32.3
Treasurer/Secretary	21	7.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

Conduct of Meetings

Regular conduct of the group meetings was one of the cardinal principles of the SHGs. In an informal organizational structure like SHGs, regular meetings are required to perform the financial activities. A part from this, it helps members to discuss social issues with their group members. All decisions are taken and all financial transactions are made in the group meeting only. The Indira Kranthi Patham project staff advocated monthly meeting norm initially, but advocated weekly meetings since the year 2006.

Table-5
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Frequency of Meetings Organized by SHGs

Frequency of Meeting	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Weekly	13	4.3
Fortnightly	15	5.0
Monthly	239	79.7
Rarely	33	11.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

Distribution of the respondents according to the frequency of meetings organized by the SHGs is presented in the table-5. It is revealed that the group meetings are mostly conducted on monthly basis. It is found that 79.7 per cent of the SHGs conducted meetings on monthly basis, followed by 5 per cent of the groups conducted meetings on fortnightly and 4.3 per cent of respondents on weekly basis. Further, it is observed that 11 per cent of the SHGs conduct meetings rarely which mean they follow irregularity in conducting of meetings. It is concluded that 89 per cent

of the SHGs are conducting meetings regularly.

Attendance in Group Meetings

For the smooth functioning of SHGs in a democratic manner the regular attendance is an important indicator. The attendance of respondents in group meetings is given in the table-6. It is found that 82.7 per cent of respondents are attending to the group meetings regularly but 17.3 per cent of respondents were not attended to the group meetings regularly. In most of the SHGs it was found that there is a practice of imposing fine for irregular attendance of group meetings. An amount of fine varied between Rs. 1 to Rs. 5. However, it is not implemented in the most of cases by the groups.

Table-6
Distribution of the Respondents by their Attendance in SHG Meetings

Attendance in Meetings	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Regular	248	82.7
Irregular	52	17.3
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

Frequency of Savings

The most important financial functions of the SHG are implementation of the small savings scheme. Savings may be remitted by the members of SHGs either weekly or monthly. All the sample respondents are paying savings regularly in the study area. Regular contribution of savings to the SHG assists the members to increase their corpus from which they borrow for different purposes and also increase their capacity to access higher amounts of credit.

Table-7
Distribution of the Respondents by the Frequency of Savings

Frequency of Savings	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Weekly	11	3.7
Monthly	289	96.3
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

Table-7 represents the distribution of respondents according to their periodicity of savings. It is revealed that 96.3 per cent of the respondents are contributing to the savings monthly. Only 3.7 per cent of the respondents are contributing to the savings weekly. In conclusion, largest percentage of the sample respondents SHGs is mobilizing savings monthly.

MODE OF SAVINGS COLLECTION

“Savings are the route to credit” is one of the basic principles behind the formation of SHGs. As such, it is important that every member of SHG should follow certain norms regarding an amount to be saved. The common practice in any SHG is that members jointly decide the savings per month or period per member on the basis of their capacity to save. An amount of savings varies across the groups. In the study area, the savings amount varied from Rs. 30 to Rs. 200.

Table-8
Distribution of the Respondents by the Mode of Savings

Savings Amount (in Rupees)	Mode of Savings		
	Weekly	Monthly	Total Number of Respondents
Rs. 30	0 (0.00)	54 (18.0)	54 (18.0)
Rs. 50	11 (3.7)	220 (73.3)	231 (77.0)
Rs. 100	0 (0.00)	5 (1.7)	5 (1.7)
Rs. 200	0 (0.00)	10 (3.3)	10 (3.3)
Total	11 (3.7)	289 (96.3)	300 (100.0)

Source: Primary Data.

Note: Figures in parentheses are row percentages to the total.

Distribution of the respondents by the range of savings is presented in table-8. It was found that 77 per cent of the respondents save Rs. 50. Among the 77 per cent of the respondents, 3.7 per cent of respondents save Rs. 50 per week and 73.3 per cent of respondents save Rs. 50 per month. Further, it reveals that 18 per cent of the respondents save Rs. 30 per month, followed by 3.3 per cent of the respondents save Rs. 200 per month and only 1.7 per cent of the respondents save Rs. 100 per month, respectively. It is concluded that about three-fourth of the respondents save Rs. 50.

Total Savings under SHG

Regular periodicity of the savings of the respondents per week or month gradually leads to a big amount under the group. The accumulated savings are varied from the respondent to respondent. The respondent savings ranges are in between Rs. 500 to above Rs. 5,000. The details about respondents accumulated savings amount under SHG is given in table-9. It is found that 46.3 per cent of the respondents have the cumulative savings under SHG below Rs. 500. It is due to the practice of internal lending among SHG members. Further, it is shown that 29.7 per cent of the respondents have the cumulative savings between Rs. 500 to Rs. 2,000, followed by 11 per cent of the respondents have Rs. 2,000 to Rs. 3,500, 7.3 per cent of the respondents have above Rs. 5,000 and only 5.7 per cent of the respondents have Rs. 3,500 to Rs. 5,000 as cumulative savings under the SHG, respectively. It is concluded that the less cumulative savings of the respondents may due to the internal lending practices and only less percentage of respondents have highest cumulative savings.

Table-9
Distribution of the Respondents by total Savings

Accumulated Savings (in Rupees)	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Below Rs. 500	139	46.3
Rs. 500 to Rs. 2,000	89	29.7
Rs. 2,000 to Rs. 3,500	33	11.0
Rs. 3,500 to Rs. 5,000	17	5.7
Above Rs. 5,000	22	7.3
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

BANKING HABITS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Generally the SHG members need to visit the banks frequently for deposit the group savings, loan receiving and loan repayment activities. It helps the respondents to know and aware about the group activities clearly like how much savings under the group, to know about the outstanding amount of loan and when will pay the loan installment, etc. In the study area the sample respondents groups has put themselves a rule as rotation basis of the respondents to go to the banks for group activities but few of them not follow. The details of the banking habits of the respondent are presented in the table-10.

Table-10
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by the Habit of Visiting Banks

Banking Habit	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Frequently	254	84.7
Rarely	46	15.3
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

It is found that 84.7 per cent of respondents are going to the banks for group activities regularly, the rest of the respondents 15.3 per cent are rarely visited the banks. The reasons for the respondents rarely visit the banks are-- the illiteracy of the respondents and they prefer to send educated respondents or leaders for banking activities of the group.

INTERNAL LENDING AMONG SHG MEMBERS

Internal lending is another basic principle of the SHGs for building their strength to meet the emergency needs of their members. The SHG group utilizes their savings for internal lending. The quantum of internal group loan to be given on the basis of interest rate, purpose, repayment period and installment are decided by the group members in the group meeting after a thorough appraisal of the borrower and his integrity in functioning with the group. In periodic meetings of the groups the internal loan requests of the respondents are considered. The details about internal

lending practices of the respondents are presented in the table-11.

Table-11
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by the Internal Lending among SHG Members

Internal Lending	Yes	No	Total
Practiced in the SHG	281 (93.7)	19 (6.3)	300 (100.0)
Utilization	220 (73.3)	80 (26.7)	300 (100.0)

Source: Primary Data.

Note: Figures in parentheses are row percentages to the total.

Table-11 reveals that 93.7 per cent of the respondents have the internal lending practices in their group, only 6.3 per cent of the respondents groups did not follow the internal lending. Among the 281 respondents who were following the internal lending practices only 220 respondents have taken internal lending amount for their needs. It is also observed that 73.3 per cent respondents have utilized internal loans and 26.7 per cent of the respondents do not utilized the internal loan from the SHGs. It is concluded that in the sample respondents nearly three-fourth of the respondents are utilized the internal loans amount for their needs.

RATE OF INTEREST CHARGED ON INTERNAL LOAN

Based on the necessity of money to a member, sample respondents groups given the priority to the member to provide internal loans among the group members. Internal loans are given mainly on trust with minimum documentation without security. The rate of interest charging pattern is varied among the groups from no interest to 24 per cent per annum. Regarding the information about the rate of interest rate charged on internal loans is given in the table-12.

Table-12
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Percentage of Interest Rates Practiced by SHG

Rate of Interest (in per cent)	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
Free of Cost	19	6.3
12	176	58.7
18	13	4.3
24	92	30.7
Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

It is evident that 58.7 per cent of the groups charged 12 per cent per annum as interest on the internal loans of the group. Further, it reveals that 30.7 per cent of the groups charged 24 per cent per annum as interest rate on the internal loans, followed by 4.3 per cent of groups charged 18 per cent of interest per annum. Only 6.3 per cent of respondents groups have not taken any interest on the

internal loans which means there is no interest rate for internal loans in those groups. It is concluded that 94.7 per cent of the groups have charged interest rate for the internal loans. This ensures the proper maintenance of the savings of the group.

SHG-BANK LINKAGE

The SHG bank linkage is providing financial services to the poor in a sustainable manner leading to empowerment of the members of the SHG. Under SHG Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP) SHGs usually get the first credit linkage between six months to one year. As the age of the SHGs increases, the member of linkages also increases.

Table-13
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Bank Linkage

Number of Bank Linkages	Number of Respondents
4 th	227 (75.7)
5 th	44 (14.7)
6 th	29 (9.7)
Total	300 (100.0)

Source: Primary Data.

Note: Figures in parentheses are percentages to total.

The distribution of the sample respondents by the bank linkage pattern is presented in the table-13. The table shows that out of total 300 respondents 75.7 per cent of the respondents have taken four bank linkages, followed by 14.7 per cent have taken five bank linkages and only 9.7 per cent of the respondents have received six bank linkages. It reveals that majority of the respondents received four bank linkages or four doses of loans from the bank.

AMOUNT OF CURRENT BANK LOAN

Table-14 represents the current bank linkage amount pattern of the respondents. It is inferred that, out of 300 respondents 47.3 per cent of the respondents have received amount ranging between Rs. 15,000 to Rs. 30,000, followed by 29.7 per cent have received the bank loan amount below Rs. 15,000, 20.7 per cent of the respondents got loan amount between Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 45,000 and only 2.3 per cent of respondents have received the bank loan amount above Rs. 45,000.

Table-14
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Current Bank Loan

Range of Bank Loan Amount (in Rupees)	Number of Respondents
Below Rs. 15,000	89 (29.7)
Rs. 15,000 to Rs. 30,000	142 (47.3)
Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 45,000	62 (20.7)
Above Rs. 45,000	7 (2.3)
Total	300 (100.0)

Source: Primary Data.

Note: Figures in parentheses are percentages to total.

Training

Rural development institutes at the central level like National Institute of Rural Development (NIRD), at the state level Andhra Pradesh Academy of Rural Development (APARD) and at the district level Technology Training Development Centers (T.T.D.C) provides training facilities for the SHGs. Training is an impact factor on the income generating skills, awareness and empowerment of the women through the training programmes. Through the training programmes different groups interact with each other and find out the way of prospering their activities. They applied innovative methods in to market their activities. Thus training to the group members and exposure visits to other successfully functioning groups, are usual to achieve this end. Through training programmes involving credible resource persons, the salient concepts and other programme details can be explained to the participants.

Table-15
Distribution of the Sample Respondents by Training

Type of Training	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage to Total
About Group Activities	65	21.7
Tailoring	25	8.3
Painting	15	5.0
Papad Making	14	4.7
Leaf Making	17	5.7
Candle and Paper Bags	9	3.0
Awareness about AIDs	19	6.3
Polio Drops	27	9
Total Trained Respondents	191	63.7
Total Non-Trained Respondents	109	36.3
Grand Total	300	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

The distribution of respondents by their attended training programmes is given in the table-15. It shows that 63.7 per cent of sample respondents have attended various training programmes and 36.3 per cent of the respondents did not attend any training programmes. Among the 63.7 per cent of trained respondents 21.7 per cent did attended to the training for the group activities, followed by 9 per cent attended training about how to give polio drops, 8.3 per cent attended for tailoring, 6.3 per cent attended for awareness about aids, 5.7 per cent attended for leaf making, 5 per cent of them attended for painting, 4.7 per cent attended for the papad making and 3 per cent have taken training about candle and paper bags making. It is concluded that majority of the respondents attended the training programme.

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals that cent per cent of the SHG women have been involved in the micro credit savings. Majority of them are properly facilitated through conducting periodical meetings and training programmes for their improvement. Majority of the respondents are actively participated in group activities and follow the adequate approach by the SHGs in getting of bank linkages. Eventhough majority of the SHG women are following the SHG norms perfectly but some of the respondent's active participation in group activities was very much limited due to the lack of understanding the adequate approach of the SHGs.

SUGGESTIONS

The following suggestions are supportive to ample functioning of SHGs.

1. Efforts should be made to increase the regular participation of SHG members in group activities, since this sort of exercise will create more awareness and empowerment among them.
2. The factors responsible for poor performance of microfinance and functioning of the SHGs should be investigated, examined and analysed thoroughly in order to resolve the emerging problems, difficulties and challenges being faced.
3. Supervision should strengthen over the working of SHGs and their federations in various levels to make SHG bank linkage programme effective and sustainable.
4. Negligence in the monitoring of the SHGs by the micro-finance providers, SHG staff and DRDA, mainly in the post-disbursement period, needs to be avoided.

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